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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Kaleidoscope Womb

The mirrors are set to forge two
distinct lives to create
geometric patterns
unique. precious. fragile.

The symmetry begins to form.
The hearts beat, neural pathways begin to mirror each other
the foundation of human life
is locked into place.

Features become distinct
the woman and the man begin to feel the tumble of the glass shards
The kaleidoscope is now in full colors
ready to burst.

As it is held up to the sky
A new color is refracted, a pale of blue of a peaceful sleep,
the fiery red of the first cry, the luminous green of curiosity
A forever shifting color
never the same twice.